

THE INFLUENCE OF WORD OF MOUTH (WOM) ON FRUIT PURCHASING DECISIONS IN THE MODERN MARKET IN THE COMMUNITY SAMARINDA CITY

By

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ABSTRACT:

Word of mouth is communication by word of mouth about views or ratings of a product or service, both individually and in groups that aim to provide personal information. This research was conducted to know the effect of word of mouth (WOM) on the decision to buy fruit in the modern market in the people of Samarinda 2023. This research was conducted at the Samarinda modern market, namely at the Lembuswana Mall, Big Mall, Samarinda Central Plaza, and Robinson Mall from January until March 2023. With a population of 130 fruit consumers in the Samarinda modern market. To obtain data in this study, the authors used a questionnaire method which was given to consumers who had bought fruit at the Samarinda modern market. The collected data were then analyzed based on the results of hypothesis testing on traditional word of mouth and online word of mouth. Furthermore, the overall results of hypothesis testing showed that traditional word of mouth (X_1) that is talker, topic, taking part, and online word of mouth (X_2) that is aids providers or media, attention to other consumers, helps the company, express positive experiences, seek advice, have a positive influence on fruit purchasing decisions in the modern market in Samarinda. Thus the hypothesis was accepted. Based on the research results obtained, it is known that of the two independent variables that have adominant influence on purchasing decisions is online word of mouth because the value of the beta coefficient(standardized coefficients beta = (0,762) is greater than the value of the traditional beta coefficient of word of mouth (standardized coefficients beta=0,225).

KEYWORDS:

Influence, traditional word of mouth, online word of mouth, decision.

1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is an agricultural country that produces various kinds of agricultural commodities, one of which is fruit. Fruit plays an important role in improving the nutritional quality of the daily food needed by everyone and is a source of people's livelihood. The market for agricultural products is growing rapidly along with the increase in people's income. Initially, farmers only sold to collectors who then sold them to traditional markets and consumers bought the fruit. At a time when agricultural products are experiencing development, namely towards modern markets, including the presence of supermarkets in various regions.

The retail industry is a strategic industry for Indonesia's economic development. The less complicated characteristics of the retail industry make most Indonesians enter this business. Based on Euro Monitor data, there were 3.61 million retailers in Indonesia in 2021. This number decreased by 11.85% compared to the previous year which was 4.1 million units. Based on type, traditional retail stores accounted for 3.57 million units, 38,323 retail units in the form of convenience stores, and 1,411 retail units in the form of supermarkets. A total of 358 units are classified as retail forecourts and 285 units are hypermarkets. Meanwhile, the value of Indonesian retail sales reached US\$ 72 billion or around IDR 1,077 trillion in 2021, which has decreased slightly due to the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic [1].

During the development of the retail business in Indonesia, there are indications that the national retail industry is more driven by new players, namely modern retail compared to traditional retail. The growth of modern retail is considered to encourage changes in control of the retail market share from traditional markets to modern markets. The number of modern markets in Samarinda City in 2021 was recorded at 224 units, many of which are controlled by 3 companies, namely Indomaret, Alfamidi, and Era Mart. Several malls are shopping centers such as Bigmal, Samarinda Central Plaza, Robinson, Lembuswana, and so on [2].

In choosing a retail store, consumers have evaluation criteria including location factors, product completeness, product quality, price, service, location, and promotions. Each individual's purchasing decision is an attitude carried out by someone in choosing 2 products or services that they will consume. And each individual has different decisions or product choices according to their preferences. Before deciding to purchase a product, consumers always look for references about a product before deciding to buy that product [3].

It cannot be denied that most consumers trust opinions about a product more. In marketing terms, this phenomenon is often called word of mouth (WOM). Word of mouth is word-of-mouth communication regarding views or assessments of a product or service, either individually or in groups to provide personal information.

Word of mouth is a very effective strategy that influences consumer decisions in using products or services and word of mouth can build a sense of trust among customers. Word of mouth is divided into two, namely first, traditional word of mouth such as communication or interaction about a product or service individually or in groups that introduces a good or service, for example, social gatherings, family events, cooperation, socialization or conversations in the community and other forms of association that allow interactions to occur that introduce a product or service.

The research aims to determine the influence of word of mouth on the decision to purchase fruit in modern markets among people in Samarinda City.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

2.1. Location and Time

This research was carried out from November 2022 to March 2023 in modern markets in Samarinda, namely, Lembuswana Mall, Samarinda Central Plaza (SCP) Mall, Bigmall Samarinda and Robinson Samarinda Mall. These four places are shopping centers which are classified as modern markets that are busy with consumers inside and outside Samarinda City who shop at these places, so it is easy to get respondents who buy fruit.

2.2. Collecting data

Data collection consists of (1) primary data obtained through field research carried out directly on the research object using observation and interviews using questionnaires; and (2) secondary data obtained through literature studies in journals, books, magazines, electronic media, print media or other sources such as monographs of an agency, Central Bureau of Statistics, related agencies, encyclopedias, the internet and so on related to t-WOM, e-WOM and consumer purchasing decisions [4].

2.3. Sampling Method

The population in this study was taken from all consumers who purchased or consumed fruit at Lembuswana Mall, Samarinda Central Plaza Mall, Bigmall Samarinda, and Robinson Samarinda Mall. Sampling uses non-probability sampling, namely a sample determination technique using accidental sampling, that is, anyone who happens to meet the researcher can be used as a sample if it is seen by chance that the people they meet are suitable as data sources [4]. This research used a sample of 130 respondents, namely consumers who had bought or consumed fruit at Lembuswana Mall totaling 30 respondents, Samarinda Central Plaza Mall totaling 35 respondents, Bigmall Samarinda totaling 35 respondents and Robinson Mall Samarinda totaling 30 respondents.

In this research, the independent variables (X) are t-WOM (X_1) and e-WOM (X_2) while the dependent variable (Y) is Purchase Decision (Y). Overall there are 13 indicators between the traditional word-of-mouth variables (X_1), online word-of-mouth (X_2), and purchasing decisions (Y) are presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1. Indicators for Purchase Decision Variables (Y), Traditional Word of Mouth (X1), and Online Word of Mouth (X2).

Variable	Concept	Indicator
Y	Buying decision	1. Y = Problem recognition 2. Y = Information search 3. Y = Evaluation of alternatives 4. Y = Purchase decision 5. Y = Post-purchase behavior
X_1	Traditional Word of Mouth (t-WOM)	1. X_1 = Discussion 2. X_1 = Subject 3. X_1 = Company participation

X_2	Online Word of Mouth (e-WOM)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. X_2 = Media or assistance provider 2. X_2 = Attention to other consumers 3. X_2 = Help the company 4. X_2 = Expression of positive experience 5. X_2 = Seek Advice
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Source: Primary data processed (2023)

2.4. Data analysis method

The data measuring tool used to obtain consumer response data in this research is interval using the Bipolar Adjective technique, which is a refinement of the semantic scale with the hope that the resulting response can be internally scale data [5]. The scale used is in the range 1-10. The use of a scale of 1-10 (even scale) is to avoid respondents who tend to choose answers in the middle so that it will produce responses that are clustered in the middle (gray area). The measurements on this scale only use two extreme categories, namely, strongly disagree and strongly agree (Figure 1).

strongly disagree	□	□	□	□	□	□	□	□	□	□	□	Strongly Agree
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10		

Figure 1. Interval scale measurement

2.4.1. Multiple Linear Regression Test

In this research, the independent variables (X) are t-WOM (X_i) and e-WOM (X_2) while the dependent variable (Y) is the purchasing decision (Y). The analytical tool used is Multiple Linear Regression with the help of the SPSS Statistics version 23 program. The relationship model between

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e$$

Information: Y = dependent variable (purchasing decision); a = constant; b_1, b_2 = regression coefficient; X_1 = Independent variable (Traditional Word of Mouth); and X_2 = Independent variable (Online Word of Mouth).

2.4.2. Correlation Coefficient (R)

The correlation coefficient is used to answer how close, or how strong the linear relationship is between the independent (X) and the dependent (Y). The calculation of the Correlation Coefficient is expressed using the following formula [7]:

$$R = \frac{b_1 \sum X_1 Y + b_2 \sum X_2 Y + b_3 \sum X_3 Y + b_4 \sum X_4 Y}{\sum Y^2}$$

To be able to provide an interpretation of whether the correlation coefficient found is large or small, you can look at the provisions listed in the following Table 2 :

Table 2. Guidelines for Interpreting Correlation Coefficients

Interval Correlation Coefficient	Relationship level
0,00- 0,199	Very low
0,20–0,399	Low
0,40–0,599	Currently
0,60- 0,799	Strong
0,80–1,000	Very strong

Source : [4]

2.4.3. Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Determinant coefficient calculations are used to measure the magnitude of the influence between two or more variables. The R^2 calculation uses the following formula [7] :

$$R^2 = \frac{SSR}{TotalSS}$$

Information: SSR = Sum of Squares Regression; and Total SS = Total Sum of Squares

2.4.4. F-test (simultaneous)

The F test is used to test the effect of regression coefficients together, with the following formula [7]:

$$F_h = \frac{R^2 / k}{(1 - R^2) / (n - k - 1)}$$

Information : R^2 = Multiple correlation coefficient n; n = Number of sample members, and k = Number of independent variables

The examiner's criteria are as follows:

Ho: $\beta = 0$ (traditional word of mouth and online word of mouth does not affect purchasing decisions.

Ha: Traditional word of mouth and online word of mouth influence purchasing decisions.

Ho is accepted if F-count > F-table. Ha is rejected if F-count < F-table.

2.4.5. T-test (partial)

The t-test is used to determine whether, in the regression model, the independent variables ($X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_n$) partially have a significant effect on the dependent variable (Y). With the following formula [7]:

$$t_{\text{count}} = \frac{b_i}{S_{b_i}}$$

Information: B_i = regression coefficient of variable I; S_{b_i} = standard error of variable i

The t-test results can be seen in the Output Coefficients from multiple linear regression analysis. Test criteria:

Ho is accepted if t-count $\leq$ t-table

Ho is rejected if t-count > t-table.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Research Results

3.1.1 General description of fruits in the modern market

Along with increasing social welfare, the demand for fruit is growing rapidly. Initially, farmers only sold to collecting traders who then sold to traditional markets where consumers bought the fruit. Currently, agricultural products are experiencing development, namely modern markets, including the presence of supermarkets in various regions to market fruit products. With the presence of modern markets, of course, the fruit sold is varied, of good quality, and packaged so that it attracts the attention of consumers. Not only that, modern markets maintain a higher level of cleanliness compared to other places selling fruit, so consumers are the ones who determine what type of fruit they want according to their daily needs.

3.1.2. General description of the research location

Central Plaza is one of the largest malls in Samarinda which was built in 1997 and is located at Jl. Pulau Irian No. 1 Karang Mumus Samarinda Ilir, East Kalimantan 75113. This mall has become the largest shopping center and Land of the Mark. This mall has been embedded in the hearts of the people of Samarinda and has been. Samarinda Central Plaza Mall has become a complete and charming shopping destination. There are quite a lot of tenants in the Samarinda Central Plaza (SCP), one of which is the Farmers Market. This farmers market is located on the first floor right in front of the entrance to the SCP mall. The fruit sold at the farm market is quite complete. Almost all fruit is sold at the farmer's market.

Robinson Samarinda Mall is a modern shopping center that has been open since 2010. This mall is located on Jl. M. Yamin, Gunung Kelua, Samarinda Ulu, Samarinda City, East Kalimantan 75243. One of the tenants at Robinson Mall is Robinson Mart. Robinson Mart is located on the bottom floor. The fruit sold here is quite complete and varied.

Bigmall Samarinda is a shopping center in Samarinda and one of the largest shopping centers in East Kalimantan. Big Mall Samarinda is a family mall with a concept to provide all the family's needs in one place. This mall is located on the edge of the famous Mahakam River on the island of Kalimantan. The facilities at this mall include a prayer room, ATM Center, Ladies' Parking, Disabled Facilities, Sitting Area, Nursery Room, Clinic, and so on. Since opening to the public in 2014, Big Mall has become the first destination for local and national visitors looking for the latest lifestyle. Big Mall is located on Jl. Untung Suropati No. 08, Karang Asam Ulu, Kec. Sungai Kunjang, Samarinda City, East Kalimantan 75243. This mall consists of 7 floors with tenants who are well-known as large companies, both national and international, one of which is Hypermart. This big mall hypermart is located on the second floor. Almost all fruit is sold at the big mall hypermarket.

3.1.2. Multiple linear regression

To empirically test the attractiveness between the independent variable (X) and the dependent variable (Y) consisting of Traditional Word of Mouth (X_1), Online Word of Mouth (X_2) on Purchasing Decisions (Y) when purchasing fruit at Lembuswana Mall, Samarinda Central Plaza Mall (SCP), Bigmall Samarinda and Robinson Samarinda Mall. The results of the Multiple Linear Regression analysis are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
	Constant	3,375	0,673		5,015	0,000
	t-WOM (X ₁)	0,371	0,093	0,225	3,978	0,000
	e-WOM (X ₂)	0,705	0,052	0,762	13,504	0,000
a. Dependent Variable: buyer's decision (Y)						
Source: Primary data (processed) 2023						

Based on the analysis results from Table 3 above, the following multiple linear equations are obtained: $Y = 3.375 + 0.371 X_1 + 0.705 X_2$. Based on the results of the regression equation above, shows that there is a positive influence between t-WOM and e-WOM on the decision to purchase fruit in the modern market, meaning that every increase and addition to the independent variable will affect the increase and addition of the independent variable which can be explained. as follows: (1) Constant (a) = 3.375 is a fixed value that cannot be influenced by the regression coefficient, namely purchasing decisions (Y) of 3.375 are the influence of other factors besides the traditional word of mouth (X₁) and online word of mouth variables (X₂); (2) Regression coefficient (X₁) = 0.371 shows that there is a positive influence between the traditional word of mouth (X_i) on purchasing decisions (Y), namely that there is more positive talk about fruit in modern markets conveyed by other people or fruit consumers. fruit can directly improve the purchasing decision process; (3) Regression coefficient (X₂) = 0.705 shows that there is a positive influence between online word of mouth (X₂) on purchasing decisions (Y), namely the more positive comments about fruit in modern markets that are conveyed via internet media, the greater the influence on the purchasing decision process is getting bigger.

3.1.3. Correlation Coefficient Test (R), Coefficient of Determination Test (R²)

Based on the results of the analysis that has been tested previously which shows that the correlation coefficient (R) value is 0.977 or 97.70%, can be explained the relationship between the whole research, namely traditional word of mouth (X₁) and online word of mouth (X₂) on purchasing decisions. (Y) fruit in the modern market has a very strong relationship because it is in the interval 0.800-1.000 as explained in Table 2 previously regarding the interpretation of the correlation coefficient.

Based on the results of the analysis, the R₂ was 0.954 or 95.4%. This shows that the percentage contribution of traditional word of mouth (X₁) and online word of mouth (X₂) to the purchasing decision process (Y) is 95.4%, where this value is included in the relatively high category. Variations in the independent variables used in the model can explain 95.4% of the variation in the dependent variable of the purchasing decision process (Y), while the remaining 4.6% of purchasing decisions are influenced by other variables not examined in this research.

3.1.4. F-test and t-test

The results of this F test can be seen in Table 4 below:

Table 4. F-Test Results

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Degree free	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1785,060	2	892,530	1326,197	.000 ^b
	Residual	85,471	127	0,673		

	Total	1870,531	129		
a. Dependent Variable: buyer's decision(Y)					
b. Predictors: (Constant), t-WOM (X ₁), e-WOM (X ₂)					

Based on the results of the analysis using the SPSS program computer tool with a significance level of 0.05 in the table above, it shows that the Fcount value is 1326.197 > than the Ftable of 3.92 (df 2 = n-k-1 so df 2 = 130- 2-1=127) with a significance probability value of 0.000, this means that the significance probability value is smaller than the value 0.5 or (0.000 < 0.05). This shows that traditional word of mouth (X₁) and online word of mouth (X₂) together (simultaneously) have a significant influence on the fruit purchasing decision process at Lembuswana Mall, Samarinda Central Plaza Mall, Samarinda Bigmall and Mall Robinson Samarinda, thus Ho was accepted.

The results of this t-test can be seen in the following Table 5:

Table 5. t-Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Mode		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3,375	0,673		5,015	0,000
	t-WOM (X ₁)	0,371	0,093	0,225	3,978	0,000
	e-WOM (X ₂)	0,705	0,052	0,762	13,504	0,000
a. Dependent Variable: buyer's decision(Y)						

Based on the results of data analysis using the SPSS program computer tool with a significance level of 0.05 or 5%, the table above shows that the t-table is 1.9788 (df 2=130-2-1=127) so it can be explained as follows:

1. The influence of traditional word of mouth on purchasing decisions

The t-count value for t-WOM (X₁) is 3.978 compared to the t-table value of 1.980 (3.978 > 0,9788). This means that t-count > t-table with a significance level of 0.000 < 0.05, so Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. This shows that t--WOM influences the decision to purchase fruit at Lembuswana Mall, Samarinda Central Plaza Mall, Bigmall Samarinda, and Robinson Samarinda Mall. Based on the regression equation, it is known that t-WOM has a positive beta coefficient value of 0.225, meaning that the more people share information or talk about the positive side of fruit in the modern market, the higher the purchasing decision.

2. The influence of online word of mouth on purchasing decisions

The t-count value for e-WOM (X₂) is 13.504 compared to the t-table value of 1.9788 (13.504 > 1.9788). This means that t-count > t-table with a significance level of 0.000 < 0.05, so Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. This shows that e-WOM influences fruit purchasing decisions at Lembuswana Mall, Samarinda Central Plaza Mall, Bigmall Samarinda, and Robinson Samarinda Mall. Based on the regression equation, it is known that e-WOM has a positive beta coefficient value of 0.762, meaning that the more people share positive information on social media about fruit in modern markets, the

higher the purchasing decision. Based on the results of online word-of-mouth hypothesis testing, it is known that of the two independent variables that have a dominant influence on purchasing decisions is online word of mouth because the beta coefficient value (Standardized coefficient Beta = 0.762) is greater than the traditional word of mouth beta coefficient value is (Standardized coefficients Beta = 0.225).

3.2. Discussion

3.2.1. The Influence of Traditional Word of Mouth on Purchasing Decisions

Based on the results of previous data processing using a questionnaire, it was found that traditional word of mouth had a positive and significant effect on the decision process for purchasing fruit at the modern market in the Samarinda community. The traditional word-of-mouth variable is said to have a positive and significant influence on the decision process to purchase fruit in modern markets because based on the data that has been collected it is known that respondents who get information about fruit in modern markets from people they know personally are more trusted.

In t-WOM communication theory, it is considered to have a strong influence on consumer purchasing decision behavior in every step, especially information search, alternative evaluation, and product choice [8]. So it can influence respondents in deciding to purchase fruit in the modern market because their close relatives can provide detailed information or explanations about fruit in the modern market both in terms of quality, price, durability, and the features contained therein. Apart from close relatives, the response or explanation from the company also has a strong influence on purchasing decisions. because the company's explanation in responding to questions regarding products or services to consumers will greatly influence consumer interest in making purchasing decisions.

The results of this research are by the three indicators [8] Talkers, namely anyone from friends, friends, neighbors, or family. Topic (subject), namely communication will arise because there is a topic that makes them talk about products or services. Taking Part (company participation) is the company's participation in responding to questions regarding products or services.

a) Talkers (talks)

Talkers, namely anyone from friends, close friends, neighbors, or family. Consumers like them are the most enthusiastic about sharing their experiences. The consumer starts a conversation telling about his experiences and knowledge about fruit in the modern market when he is in his social environment in the community, for example at events, social gatherings, family events and so on which allows interaction to occur in introducing fruits which include regarding price, quality and so on, so that other listeners have the desire to buy fruit in the modern market. There are always people who are enthusiastic to talk. The consumer starts a conversation telling about his experiences and knowledge about fruit in the modern market when he is in his social environment in the community, for example at events, social gatherings, family events and so on which allows interaction to occur in introducing fruits that include regarding price, quality and so on, so that other listeners have the desire to buy fruit on the modern market. These are the ones who are the most enthusiastic about sharing their experiences. Based on the results, it can be seen that talkers (talkers) from a total of 130 respondents filled in scores from 5-9, where 7 and 8 were the most, namely 46 and 34, which means they were categorized as strongly agree because they were getting closer to 10.

b) Topic (concerning)

Topic (concerning) that is, communication will arise because of things that make them talk about products or services. This topic relates to what a product offers. Such as special offers, discounts, new products, or the quality of the comfortable place. These consumers will discuss the discount prices of fruit sold in modern markets and also the quality of the fruit sold in modern markets. In the second indicator, traditional word of mouth, namely the number of 130 respondents who filled in scores 5-9, where scores 6 and 7 were the highest, namely 40 and 40, which means they were categorized as strongly agreeing because they were getting closer to 10.

c) Taking Part (company participation)

Taking Part (company participation) is the company's participation in responding to questions regarding products or services. A conversation will disappear if only one person participates in the conversation so that word of mouth can continue. Therefore, the Company is always willing to provide explanations regarding consumer questions regarding fruit so that consumers feel comfortable and always want to shop at modern markets. For the third indicator of t-wom, namely company participation from 130 respondents, the score consists of a score of 5-9. The most common scores are scores 6 and 7, namely 40 and 46. Based on the data measuring tool in this study, namely using the bipolar adjective technique, the closer to 10, the more you agree. The scores filled in from the three indicators in this study are getting closer to 10, which means they are appropriate. From this, it is proven that traditional word of mouth has a positive and significant influence on the fruit-purchasing decision process in the modern market among the people of Samarinda.

In t-WOM communication theory, it is considered to have a strong influence on consumer purchasing decision behavior in every step, especially information search, alternative evaluation, and product choice [8]. So it can influence respondents in deciding to purchase fruit in the modern market because their close relatives can provide detailed information or explanations about fruit in the modern market both in terms of quality, price, durability, and the features contained therein. Apart from close relatives, the response or explanation from the company also has a strong influence on purchasing decisions. The company's explanation in responding to questions about products or services to consumers will greatly influence consumer interest in making purchasing decisions.

The results of this study are in accordance with the three indicators [9] Talkers, namely anyone from friends, best friends, neighbors or family. Topic (subject), namely communication will arise because there is a topic that makes them talk about products or services. Taking Part (company participation) is the company's participation in responding to questions regarding products or services.

3.2.2. The Influence of Online Word of Mouth on Purchasing Decisions

Based on the results of data processing using a questionnaire, the majority of fruit buyers obtain information on purchasing decisions through social media. This shows that online word of mouth has a positive and significant influence on the fruit-purchasing decision process in modern markets.

The online word-of-mouth variable is said to have a positive and significant influence on the fruit-purchasing decision process in modern markets because based on the data that has been collected it can be seen that social media, including Facebook, Instagram, and especially WhatsApp, can help respondents obtain information regarding choices, quality, the price, durability, and durability of fruit in modern markets compared to traditional markets and other street fruit traders.

Through social media, respondents or consumers can share information with other consumers about fruit in the modern market so that other consumers can easily get the information they want.

Respondents also paid attention to other consumers by sharing their positive experiences when using fruit in modern markets. Respondents also felt that the information conveyed by other respondents via social media could help the company because the information obtained would help consumers decide to purchase fruit in modern markets. Through social media, respondents hope to receive advice or tips from other people who can help them in determining fruit purchasing decisions in modern markets. Respondents realized that social media is an effective medium for disseminating information about fruit in the modern market.

Based on research conducted by Thurau et al. Online word of mouth in this research uses 5 indicators [10] namely providers of assistance or media, namely the frequency of consumers visiting and writing their opinions. Attention to other consumers, namely the desire to help other people in making decisions to purchase a product. Helping the company, namely the desire to help the company by conveying a positive message as a reward from the company for being satisfied with the use of its products or services. Expressing positive experiences, namely expressing positive feelings and self improvement after using a product or service. Seeking advice, namely the hope of gaining knowledge about a product or service after interacting with other people.

a). Aid or media providers

Assistance providers or media, namely the frequency of consumers visiting and writing their opinions. Consumers who have previously purchased fruit at modern markets will provide visits or positive opinions via their social media. Based on the results, it can be seen that the first indicator of e-WOM is the provider of assistance or media. Of the 130 respondents, they filled in a score from 5-10. The highest score is 7, namely 39, which means it is categorized as strongly agree because it is getting closer to 10.

b). Attention to other consumers

Attention to other consumers, namely the desire to help other people in making decisions to purchase a product. by providing attention through online media that the fruit being sold is very conducive and of good quality and the best choice of fruit, which makes buyers decide to buy fruit in the modern market. For the second indicator, namely attention to other consumers, out of 130 respondents filled in scores from numbers 5-9. The highest score is number 7, namely 49, which means it is categorized as strongly agree because it is getting closer to number 10.

c). Helping companies

Helping the company, namely the desire to help the company by conveying a positive message as a reward from the company for being satisfied with the use of its products or services. Someone who has made a purchase will convey a positive message to the company regarding the fruit they have purchased in the modern market via their social media, for example sharing positive post-purchase experiences with their closest relatives via the WhatsApp group or also giving positive likes and comments and also sharing posts. about fruit products on the modern market. The third indicator is helping the company, the respondent's answer is on a score of 5-9, where the highest score is 7, namely 49, which means they are categorized as strongly agree because it is getting closer to 10.

d). Expressing positive experiences

Expressing experiences positively, namely expressing positive feelings and self-improvement after using a product or service. Consumers who have bought fruit in modern markets will express their positive experiences to their relatives and those closest to them about the quality of fruit in modern markets is much better than others. The fourth indicator is expressing positive experiences,

the respondents' answers are in numbers 5-9, namely the highest score is number 8, namely 41, which means they are categorized as strongly agree because it is getting closer to number 10.

e). Seek Advice

Seeking advice, namely the hope of gaining knowledge about a product or service after interacting with other people. In the context of web-based opinion platforms, consumption occurs when individuals read product reviews and comments written by others, which can also motivate consumers to write comments. Here, consumers who have purchased fruit at the modern market will provide positive comments so that people or society who read these comments will decide to buy fruit at the modern market. For the fifth indicator, namely seeking advice, the respondents' answers were at numbers 5-9, where the highest score was at number 6 for 40 respondents. Based on the data measuring tool in this research, namely using the bipolar adjective technique. The closer to 10, the more you are categorized as strongly agreeing. The scores for the three indicators in this study are getting closer to 10, which means they agree. From this, it is proven that e-WOM has a positive and significant influence on the fruit-purchasing decision process in the Modern Market among the Samarinda Community.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Based on the results of hypothesis testing on t-WOM, it is proven that it influences the decision to purchase fruit in the modern market among the Samarinda community. Thus the first hypothesis in this research is accepted.
2. Based on the results of hypothesis testing on e-WOM, it shows that it is proven to influence the decision to purchase fruit at the modern market among the Samarinda community. Thus, the second hypothesis in this study is accepted. Thus, it is known that of the two independent variables that have a dominant influence on purchasing decisions is e-WOM because the Beta coefficient value (Standardized Beta coefficients) = 0.762 is greater than the traditional word of mouth beta coefficient value (Standardized coefficients Beta = 0.225).

4.2. Suggestion

Based on the results of the discussion and conclusions in this research, the following suggestions can be put forward:

1. For retail companies, consumer purchasing decisions are influenced by word of mouth, both traditional and online, which is more dominant than e-WOM, so it is recommended that companies carry out more online promotions on social media.
2. The size of consumers' fruit purchasing decisions can be influenced by word of mouth in the modern market, so it is hoped that retail companies will not ignore t-WOM and e-WOM so that sales results increase and maintain the quality of the fruit sold to consumers. Suggestions for future researchers that are relevant to this title, it is hoped that researchers can use this research as comparative material to carry out subsequent research and can add other variables apart from the variables in this research with different analysis methods so that they will get varied results and can improve the results of this research.

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